

THE ESSENCE OF EDUCATION IN SPECIALIZED EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS FOR CHILDREN WITH SPECIAL EDUCATION NEEDS

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Abstract: This article contains opinions about the content and essence of providing education to children with special educational needs. Also, the essence of education of specialized boarding schools is explained.

Key words: Educational system, L.Vygotsky, inclusive education, pedagogical technology, Presidential Decision.

The issue of education of children with special needs is becoming one of the most urgent issues today. Special education has developed as an educational system for children with disabilities. It is built on the assumption that the needs of children with disabilities cannot be met in general education institutions. Special education operates all over the world in the form of schools or boarding schools, as well as small parts of general education schools.

In the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 13, 2020 No. PQ-4860 "On measures to further improve the system of education for children with special educational needs", "Education of children with disabilities Creation of alternative forms of education and training, implementation of innovative and information and communication technologies for comprehensive comprehensive development of this category of children" were identified as priority tasks. As a result, ample opportunities have been created to provide deaf and hard-of-hearing children with all-round quality education in our country, as well as to improve the mechanisms. The implementation of the educational system should always be based on certain laws, principles and foundations. Today, about 250,000 disabled children (under 16 years old) need education in Uzbekistan. Taking this into account, special educational institutions for children with disabilities operate in our republic. In addition, various decisions and laws have been developed in the countries of the world, including Uzbekistan, on the implementation of inclusive education.

Inclusion is used both broadly and narrowly. In a broad sense, it means children with special needs who are victims of war, children who are refugees, children from low-income families, children from socially vulnerable families, gifted children, children with health problems and those with disabilities. Ideas of

inclusive education are based on socio-cultural theories. Psychologist L.Vygotsky (1986-1934) is the founder of the idea of inclusive education, and through his theory of social constructivism, children learn most effectively in a social environment. L. Vygotsky said that the development of higher mental functions begins with social cooperation and then becomes personal. Thus, this social interaction is always the main method of development and learning. He also believed that education precedes development. Adults can encourage learning by paying attention to the skills or knowledge of the child in the "zone of immediate development". L.Vygotsky defines the "zone of such development" as what the child knows or can do and does or understands with the help of a competent person. defined as a possible field or space.

L. Vygotsky's theory of social and cultural development clearly defines the role of the pedagogue. We need to know our children well and actively communicate with them to determine their educational activities within the framework of the "immediate development center". If children learn primarily through social interaction, we educators must maximize the time a child interacts with other children and adults. My preschooler's noisy (but not loud), busy (but not chaotic) group is a normal learning environment. The practice of inclusive education in many countries has shown the correctness of this theory. According to research, children with special needs study together with their peers. Tend to show better results in learning and social communication.

All children benefit from inclusive education practices. Usually, a child with special needs, being in a group with developing peers, tries to imitate them, communicate with them, and develop social skills. Developing children understand the challenges faced by people with special needs. They are sensitive to the needs of others and better understand the differences. They learn that all people can overcome important problems and achieve success. It is also beneficial for educators to have children with special needs on their team, where they can gain skills in observing differences in learning styles. They also become more confident in assessing children's individual strengths and identifying areas that need support. This allows educators to identify a child's individual strengths and special needs and improve their learning based on that. Inclusive education means recognizing that children are different from each other in many ways and that these differences are not obstacles, but valuable resources. Children's different learning needs and abilities and their different developmental rates can be met by individualizing and differentiating learning activities and learning strategies.

Specific characteristics of inclusive preschool education organizations:

- general education of children with special needs is carried out by a team of specialists together with pedagogues in regular groups;
- it is necessary to determine how many children with special needs can be successfully included in one group.

Usually, this amount depends on the type of characteristics of each child and the support the pedagogue receives from his preschool education organization. For example, with the help of other specialists, a pedagogue can take only one child with a serious disease or several children with a mild diagnosis into his group. There is a practice of including children with special needs, who do not exceed 5-10% of the total number of children in the group. If there are 20 children in the group, admission of 1-2 children with special needs:

- ❖ active participation of parents and other family members in making decisions about their children's education and development;
- ❖ all pedagogues (group educator, preschool psychologist or defectologist, music director, physical education instructor) work as a team and coordinate their efforts.
- ❖ Decisions are made by team members who work effectively with each other;
- ❖ strategies and education ensure the development of whole children and take into account the special developmental needs of each individual child;
- ❖ work with children with special needs is designed taking into account the individual child's development map, children's strengths and needs;
- ❖ the effectiveness of the programs is regularly evaluated; all interested parties are involved (family members, pedagogues, other specialists);

All pedagogues should have an understanding of the characteristics of teaching and development of children with special needs, undergo special training and improve their skills, learn special education.

Types of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The goal of inclusive education	
Tasks of inclusive education	

As a conclusion, we can say that the experiments conducted on the implementation of Inclusive education have proven that if any disability of children with disabilities is detected in time and referred to specialists from an early age, and the work of preparing for school is completed. If it is carried out at the right time, it is possible to achieve the intended goal. That is, the effectiveness of inclusive education will be high.

References:

1. Law on Education" of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Tashkent, 2020.

- 2.Kharatova, S. (2022). PERSONAL QUALITIES AND JOBS. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 1(5), 51-55.
- 3.Shomakhmudova R. "Special and inclusive education" educational methodical manual.
- 4.Kharatova, S. K., & Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. Science and Education, 3(3), 713-718.
- 5.Vygotsky L.S. Defect and overcompensation. // "The problem of defectology". M., 1996. -S. 42.
- 6.Kharatova, S. K. (2021). TENDENCIES OF DEVELOPMENT OF DISTANCE EDUCATION IN GLOBAL TRANSFORMATION. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 1(10), 353-362.
- 7.Kryzhanovskaya L.M. Psychological correction in conditions of inclusive education. Handbook for psychologists and teachers. - M.: "Vlados", 2013. 83-b.
- 8.Kharatova, S. K. (2022). Characteristics of the pedagogical process system. Science and Education, 3(6), 681-686.
- 9.S.S. Akbarov. Legal basis for involving children with disabilities in inclusive education. Proceedings of the international scientific-practical online conference "Inclusive education: strategy, science, practice and technologies". 60 pages. December 10, 2021.

